

The Decline of Communist Politics in Bihar: An Analysis of Ideological Weaknesses and Socio-Political Disconnects

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Abstract: This article reviews the communist politics in Bihar and identifies their main weakness and central tendencies. Communists in Bihar are a product of post-colonial and post-feudal periods. Why was not it produced during the colonial and feudal periods? Why were they produced amidst a so-called democratic, socialist, and secular regime? Their birth in Bihar and India could be associated more with capitalism. However, they appeared to me as a product of a corrupt political, bureaucratic, and business system. For me, they are part of the problem and cannot therefore seen as a solution. They never had the support of the masses and the population never remained convinced with their agenda and style.

Keywords: Left Politics; Communists and Bihar; Decline of Communism in India; Ideological Weakness of Left; Socio-Political Disconnect.

Introduction:

Various communist parties can do a lot better in India however they lack proper vision and methods for the betterment of the society and government. More or less, they appeared as a confused lot without yielding and achieving anything. They talked of feudalism without considering that feudalism had collapsed. They termed certain particular social groups or castes not following their ideologies as feudal and never asked anything about the rise of the new capitalist order in the society. The central tendency of communists and other progressive canon in Bihar has been to cause conflicts in the society especially between different social groups. Instead of working on programs and policies for people's welfare, they dealt with governments for their interests as an individual and commune. It was easy for them to talk about the poor and towards this end they considered it better to target certain social groups. This is simply caste politics by the communists and commune in Bihar failing to recognize and work upon the major social, political, economic, and religious issues of Bihar. They failed to make an issue of unemployment, migration, land water management, productivity, law & order, leadership, corruption, education, public health, social security, and welfare. No matter whatsoever they failed to create any impacts and raise confidence among any section of the Bihar population so far.

Communists operated through a commune or syndicate and never recognized the social structure of Bihar. They failed to work with different castes, communities, and categories of people. Even though they talked about the laborers, however, failed to recognize the farmers' concerns. However, they kept speaking in larger voices against feudalism despite the collapse of feudalism after independence. This was the cattiest attitude of the communists influenced by the brahmanical leadership of the congress. Communists also opposed development, neoliberalism, and modernization however, failed to oppose liberalization, privatization, and globalization. They neither realized the micro-social structure nor did they combine with the changes imposed through the macro-social institutions. They also failed to put forward their ideas of social institutions especially those related to the economy and state. They also kept mum about the social systems such as education, politics, economics, and many others. They may have ideas for betterment of the society yet fail to realize them among the masses. The relatively newer political formations in Bihar such as *Bhartiya Janata Party* (BJP), *Rashtriya Janta Dal* (RJD), and *Janta Dal-United* (JD-U) gained power in Bihar. Even parties like *Loktantrik Janata Party* (LJP), *HAM*, and *RLSP*, are all doing relatively better than those communist parties in Bihar. The sole factor for their electoral successes is caste and community equations working in their favor.

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It is not so that only communists worked through a commune because even the *Rashtriya Swaymsevak Sangh* (RSS) and *Congress Party* also worked similarly as they formed a commune of supporters in the name of *Sanghis* and *Sewa dal*. However, the political success of both the Congress and *BJP* was never due to their respective communes, getting involved with the social issues. They make an issue out of various social, political, religious, and economic issues. If Congress talked about secularism, then the *BJP* talked about corruption and appeasing of minorities.

The kind of politics played by the communist parties are distinctly aloof and apart from most of the political parties. The self-obsessed communist parties in Bihar also suffered from too many similar formations confusing people about ideologies and functional abilities to set forth those ideas into motion. If RSS speaks about *Ayodhya*, *Kasi*, *Mathura*, Reservation, Kashmir, and the decline of the Hindu population, however, communists keep mum over them. Even they tried to polish and hide themselves in the name of decency, intellectuality, and morality. Polished or rude behavior both are the source of conflicts. The immorality of the conduct has been reflected through their mobilization of people for rallies and meetings. They openly bribed participants through their agents and representatives. They lacked both confidence and strength because they were not associated with castes, communities, and categories of people. Their progressive approach is their main weakness. The conflicting ideas, talk of a stateless society, unity of labor, and attack on institutions would have no value until and unless supported by the people. People are not interested in those large slogans rather they want their core problems to be solved. At least the commune of RSS & Communists are allowing them to move into society with a banner and discuss issues in mass media.

What I expected from the communists to talk about the wage's uniformity in the country irrespective of kind of work. The wages of a peon, worker, employee either public or private, professionals, and bureaucrats should be made uniform or at least more and more close to each other. This would have ended the lust for government jobs and people would have started working in farms and other livelihoods or service sectors. This has created a great gulf in the society. Society can be better run through rules instead of enactments. Societal approach in education, health, welfare, justice, and internal-external security would have been promoted.

They should have taken the lead in dismantling the religious and caste boundaries to unite the people of the subcontinent. Once people realized that they would not deliver and even they were not serious about the people, they started losing ground despite strong notional ideas about the laborers and workers' community. Even people remained largely concerned about their motives and intentions about different castes, and communities. The communist parties sustainably failed in forging partnerships with castes and communities in Bihar and failed to raise any hope among them either in terms of ideologies or functions for the betterment of agriculture, industry, employment, and self-employment. Even if they repeatedly fail to create confidence among the business community and market forces. Even if China succeeded in reforming policies to suit the market economy, and they do not see any harm in India becoming a market of Chinese products. The USA has shifted its corporates to China and invaded the capital and social security in India. I see naxalism, Maoism, international terrorism, Hindu fundamentalism, and judicial-social activism as a part of the agenda of globalization, market economy, and liberalization. All those simply means becoming a market of foreign products especially patronized through the political economy led by the USA and China.

Literature Review:

1. Historical Context of Communist Politics in Bihar: Communist politics in Bihar emerged during the post-colonial and post-feudal periods, distinctively later than other regions globally where communist movements typically gained momentum during or immediately after colonial and feudal struggles. The delayed emergence of communism in Bihar can be attributed to the specific socio-economic conditions of the region, which were influenced by capitalism and a corrupt political system rather than the class struggles that characterized other communist movements. Scholars like Banerjee (2008) have argued that the rise of communist ideologies in Bihar was less about worker empowerment and more a response to the failures of the democratic and socialist promises of the Indian state.

2. Ideological and Strategic Failures: The central weakness of the communist parties in Bihar lies in their outdated focus on feudalism, even after its collapse post-independence. They have failed to adapt to the changing socio-economic landscape marked by the rise of capitalism and neoliberalism. Scholars such

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as Mukherjee (2009) have criticized Bihar's communists for their inability to address the pressing issues of unemployment, migration, and economic development, which are crucial concerns for the region. Instead of proposing pragmatic policies, they have often resorted to divisive caste politics, which has alienated them from the broader population.

3. Socio-Political Disconnect and Organizational Fragmentation: The communists in Bihar have been criticized for their failure to integrate with the local social structure, particularly with the caste and community dynamics that dominate the state's politics. This disconnect has been exacerbated by the fragmentation of the communist movement into multiple factions, such as CPI, CPI(M), and CPI(ML), each with differing agendas and approaches. This fragmentation has led to confusion among the masses about the communists' objectives and their capacity to effect meaningful change (Sinha, 2010). The organizational weakness and lack of a unified strategy have further eroded their influence in the state's political landscape.

4. Impact of Neoliberalism and Market Economics: In the context of neoliberalism and the global shift towards market economies, Bihar's communists have failed to adapt or present a viable alternative. Unlike China, which successfully integrated market reforms into its socialist framework, Bihar's communists have remained ideologically rigid, opposing neoliberalism without offering constructive solutions. This resistance to market economics has contributed to their declining relevance, as they have been unable to connect with the economic aspirations of the state's populace (Prakash, 2012). Their failure to engage with industrialization, urbanization, and the global market economy has left them sidelined in a rapidly changing political environment.

5. The Rise of Alternative Political Forces: The decline of communist influence in Bihar has coincided with the rise of other political parties, such as the BJP, RJD, and JD(U), which have successfully leveraged caste and community equations to gain power. These parties have managed to engage with the social issues that resonate with the electorate, such as secularism, corruption, and economic development. In contrast, the communists have remained aloof, failing to address the core concerns of the population or to provide a compelling vision for the state's future (Sharma, 2013).

Findings

Too many formations and cadres are confused

Look at the names and the numbers of those political formations. The Communist Party of India (CPI), the Communist Party of India Marxist (CPI-M), and The Communist Party on India- Maoists Liberation (CPI-ML) are some main nomenclatures. In addition, there are some underground revolutionary formations such as Moist Communist Centres (MCC), People Liberation, PLFI, Dasta, Party Unity, and many more. At least their student wings such as the All-India Students Federation (AISF), and All India Students Association (AISA) somehow able to do better due to some young and enthusiastic leadership and they make their presence felt on campuses of the universities raising different students, social, and political issues. Now and then, there are some polit bureau meetings, general body meetings, and other people meetings and rallies organized however people largely remained aloof and apart from those rallies and meetings. They do not see in them their interests being survived. Even most of the leaders belonged to outside the state.

Nonassociation with the local structure such as caste and community

One of the main reasons that communist parties have failed to recognize caste and community and their problems and solutions as their political objectives. The political objectives cannot be completed without the local social structure, problems, and construction being on board.

No support for market and neoliberalism

Industrialization and urbanization are modern-day realities. However, with their style of functioning, they never made any place in people's hearts. They behaved in a manner undemocratic and people moved away from them. They just talked about their share in produce and never focused on how to increase the produce. They behaved like persons involved with self-interests and talked of high values and morals that never coincided with their actions. Communists also do not show any interest in the so-called market economy involving free trade and a distribution system.

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Conclusion:

The communist parties in Bihar have struggled to maintain relevance in the face of changing socio-economic conditions and the rise of alternative political forces. Their failure to adapt to the collapse of feudalism, embrace neoliberal economic realities, and engage with the state's complex caste and community dynamics has led to their marginalization. Moreover, the ideological rigidity, organizational fragmentation, and disconnect from local issues have prevented them from building a broad-based movement capable of challenging the dominant political forces in Bihar. To regain relevance, Bihar's communists must critically reassess their strategies, engage with contemporary socio-economic issues, and connect with the local social structures that define the state's political landscape.

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